

Women in Higher Education: Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract

Education is the power which shapes the future of every individual. It is considered as a ladder for the improvement of women and their status by providing occupational opportunities and social mobility. It is considered that education particularly higher education is necessary for both men and women for an interesting and intelligent living. This higher education makes them to be a good citizen of the country, thereby helps in nation building. Literacy rate of the country depends on education. This paper analyses the opportunities and challenges that are available to women and the status they occupy in the field of higher education. Higher education for women is vital because it accelerates social transformation. We know the saying that educating a woman is like educating the whole family. But unfortunately, certain barriers like multiple role, lower level of self-confidence, financial constraint, lack of support from family and society, gender disparity etc., prevents women from doing their higher education. The status of women in Higher education should be raised and given more importance for it promotes both the individual and development of the nation. Women should be aware about the developmental opportunities and governmental policies that are available in the society. Higher education thus empowers women to face the world of opportunities and challenges.

Keywords: Women, status, barriers, opportunities, empowerment.

Higher Education has become a basic need for women in this ever-changing social, economic and technological scenario. The main purpose of higher education is to educate, prepare and qualify women to work in economy and socialize with the people in the society. It plays a key role in shaping the society. Higher Education can be considered as a best investment for any individual, particularly women as it provides more job opportunities and helps them lead a comfortable life. An educated woman remains positive, strong and confident. Education helps not only in the development of the woman but also helps in the development of the country by raising the per capita income of the country. Such an education should be provided to women without any discrimination. There are several barriers like gender discrimination, lack of facilities, lack of family support, early marriage, childbearing etc., which prevent the women from continuing their education. Educating women is important because educating women accelerates social transformation in the society.

“ If you educate a man, you educate an individual ; education contributes to his individual growth; it becomes his ‘private property’, as it were. But when you educate a woman, you educate the entire family” - Dada J.P. Vaswani.

As J.P Vaswani refers in her quote that when we educate a man, it contributes only to his growth and development and remains as a private property. But when a woman is educated it gets spread to the whole family. The woman educates the entire family with the knowledge she acquires. When each family of the country is educated it brings in a socioeconomically developed society. Higher education is such a powerful tool to bring in the socio economical development in the society and acts as a vehicle for social mobility for the deprived and marginalized classes of the society, especially women. Women are the weaker sections of the society who have limited access to higher education. There are several reasons that acts as a barrier for the participation and enrollment of women in higher education.

The first and foremost reason for less enrollment of women in higher education is financial constraint of the family. Women find it difficult to afford the fee structure quoted for higher education. Parents think that it is not necessary for women to pursue higher education and they are not ready to spend more on educating the females in the family. Rather they want to make use of that amount in marrying her to a groom in a decent family. A Few parents who are able to afford the fees are also not willing to educate their daughters because they feel that they might not find an equal match to their daughter if she pursues higher degree. Also, it would be difficult for them to face their relatives and people in the society if her marriage is going to get delayed.

The other challenge which women face in higher education is gender inequality. Girl children are not valued equal to boys’ right from their birth due to cultural and economic reasons. They don’t receive the same emotional and educational attention as their male counterparts. Women are considered as burden from the start and not as a blessing. More importance is given to her matrimony and motherhood rather than her education. They are made to take up multiple roles in their life which is another challenge for women in pursuing her higher education. Women are made to perform household chores, looking after their parents, siblings, elders and children etc., They don’t get enough time to concentrate and pursue their higher education. The family does not support the women in the family to educate. Even if a family is ready to offer the support in educating the females, this society and the people in it prevent them from doing so through religious, cultural and economic policies. Thus, women are deprived from pursuing higher education.

Lack self-confidence in their ability also acts a bigger challenge in pursuing higher education. Many women have low level of confidence in pursuing higher education and express high levels of anxiety. This lack of self confidence in their ability allows a negative feedback to undermine their self-esteem which affects them from enrolling themselves in higher education. This lack of confidence even affects the performance of women who have enrolled in higher education and make them drop out of college. Women must overcome all these barriers and challenges in order to improve the potential of themselves which in turn improves the prospect of the entire community.

Higher education helps women to be mentally and emotionally strong. It provides them the Knowledge which gives life to every woman. Higher education leads women to a complete living with ethical, spiritual, social and intellectual ethics and self -confidence. It helps them to maintain and preserve their life and future. Through higher education women understand the social and political structure beyond their home and act as wise citizens of the country. Women can provide good health care and financial support to their families.

Though there are several challenges and issues attached to female in higher education, Women education and the status of women in higher education has been improved through the ages. During the Vedic period women had access to education and they enjoyed equal position and rights, but

they had gradually lost their right. The position of women started to decline after 500 BC. Different customs and conventions of diverse religions like Christianity, Islam and Hinduism deteriorated the freedom, rights and state of women in the country. Later various movements launched during the colonial era witnessed an essential expansion in educating women. This influenced Modern education system.

At present, the government has taken several measures to provide education to women in the country as a result of which the literacy rate of women has increased in the modern times. The government has provided easy and ready access to student loans that would increase the ability of the needy women students to cover the expenses in higher education. The government has introduced 'Swami Vivekananda Fellowship For Single Girl Child For Research In Social Sciences' which aims to compensate direct cost of higher education particularly girls who are the only girl child of the family. The government has constituted several committees and commissions like 'Kothari Commission' and 'National policy on education' to emphasis on the promotion of gender equity in education. These commissions were formulated to neutralize the disadvantages of the past by changing the status of women.

Indian government encourages higher education for women through programme like "Post-Graduate Indira Gandhi Scholarship For Single Girl Child" which aims at encouraging and promoting higher education among women and their parents/guardians. HRDC and UGC has presented number of schemes supporting girl students to take up higher studies. UGC has provided special schemes for promotion of women's' hostels in universities and colleges and has established day cares centers. PRAGATHI is another scholarship that is implemented by AICTE for assistance of girls pursuing technical education. The government also has taken another initiative to increase the enrollment of women in higher education. It has decided to create supernumerary seats in undergraduate programmes of institutions like National Institute of Technology and Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology etc., There are funds provided under Post- Doctorate Fellowships for Women and Single Girl Child Schemes for increasing the participation of women in higher education. Government has constructed 7 universities exclusively for women to raise the enrollment of women in higher education. 'Equal Opportunity cells', 'Residential Coaching Academy' has been established to prepare minority student and women in higher education for NET, UPSC exams and PG exams.

Higher education helps women to gain knowledge as well as enable her to earn a living. An educated woman plays a vital role in a family and her education helps in preserving her life. Higher education helps women to tackle the obstacles and empower themselves to take up their full place in the society. Though women have right to education, there seems to be significant educational inequalities and challenges impacting women in higher education. Women must be made aware of the importance of higher education and women empowerment. Women should be made to realize and understand the available opportunities to pursue their higher education. They should be made aware of the schemes and programmes formulated by the government for their development and participation in higher education. With all these scholarships and accommodations provided by the government women will be able to overcome the challenges and barriers in pursuing higher education. Parents and the people in society should be motivated to understand the importance of educating women. To conclude, higher education of woman plays a significant role in improving the living standards of the country. Higher literacy rate of women improves the quality of life of home and the society. Higher education of Women must be encouraged and promoted for the empowerment of women as well as the economic growth of the country.

References

1. Government of India, All India Survey on Higher Education, 2015, Statistical Organization, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation.
2. Kumar, J. and Sangeeta (2013), “Status of women education in India”, Educational Confab, Vol. 2, No 4, Pp 162-176.
3. Moore, Kathryn M. “Women’s Access and Opportunity in Higher Education: toward the Twenty First Century.” *Comparative Education*, vol. 23, no. 1, 1987, pp. 23–34., doi:10.1080/0305006870230104.
4. Rani, Hari Ponnamma, and Madhavi Kesari. *Women in Higher Education in India: Perspectives and Challenges*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2018.